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ABSTRACT

Nowadays translation of phraseological units is an important subject for contemporary translation studies. Therefore, this subject is being discussed by translato­logists and it is closely connected with the fact that translator should interpret the meaning of the whole expression or a group of words and the primary task for the translator is to choose a meaningful equivalent for the adequate translation of a definite phraseological unit during the translation process. The translator should define the ways of translation and express the connotative and evaluation functions of the whole expression.

INTRODUCTION

Many famous and outstanding translato­logists consider that phraseological units are “translator’s false friends”, which represent some phraseological units of the source text and these phraseological units in whole or in part coincide with the units of the target text and the analysed phraseological units can create false associations during the translation process due to the reason of their similarity with free collocations. Phraseological units - “translator's false friends” - have a definite meaning and this meaning can definitely or particularly differ from the meaning of a phraseological unit in the target text.

Many linguists believe that, phraseological units are word combinations, the meaning of which is defined according to the whole expression but not according to their components or language parts. With relation to notional component binding, phraseological units should be divided into figurative and nonfigurative. Non-figurative phraseological units are called as phraseological collocations. Analysing these phraseological units, we mention that their language components express their meaning, but these units collocate with definite words and the translator cannot change them: «принимать меры» - “to take measures”, «принимать решение» - “to take a decision”.¹

Emotional expressiveness and brevity of though expression are the most distinctive

¹ Kuzmin, S. S. (2007). Idiomatic Translation from Russian into English (Theory and Practice) (pp. 7291). Moscow: Flinta: Nauka

features of phraseological units. Phraseological units are functioning in the newspaper style, notably in the newspaper headlines due to the fact that newspaper headlines are expressive and concise. As a rule, newspaper headlines grab reader's attention and reflect the author's attitude towards the events described in the article.

It should be noted that phraseological units are frequently changing into clichés. Therefore, defining phraseological units in the source text and the ability to find a corresponding equivalent during the translation process are the most tangible stages for the translator. However, translator should use phrase- books for the purpose of adequate interpretation and translation of phraseological units and, in addition, the context plays an important role in the translation process.

According to S.S. Kuzmin, interpretation of notional "conflicts between literal meaning of phraseological unit components and notional elements of the context, which have a conflict with literal meaning of phraseological unit components, is the most important stage for the translator's analysis .

According to S.S. Kuzmin, phraseological synonyms are approximately meaningful but imaginary different phraseological units. There are some examples and analyses of the Russian synonyms: «в мгновение ока», «в два счета», «одним махом», «в один момент» and the enumeration of the English synonyms: "in the twinkling of an eye", "in the nick of time", "in the turn of a hand", "in less than no time", "in a flash", "in a trice", "at the drop of a hat", "at a moment's notice".²

Analysing the abovementioned phraseological synonyms, it should be noted that all of these phraseological units have different connotations.

TYPES OF PHRASEOLOGY:

There are three types of categories regarded as part and parcel of the phraseology of any language. According to prof. A.V.Kunin, they are:

- phraseological units, or idioms, with completely or partially transferred meanings, e.g. a smart Aleck; Tom, Dick and Harry; Do you see any green in my eye?
- semi-idioms that have both literal and transferred meanings, e.g. chain reaction (a term in physics and a figurative expression), lay down one's arms (a military term and a figurative expression);
- phraseomatic units have literal or phraseomatically bound meanings, e.g. in a hurry,

² Kuzmin, S. S. (2007). Idiomatic Translation from Russian into English (Theory and Practice) (pp. 7291). Moscow: Flinta: Nauka

safe and sound, pay attention to smth.³

In conclusion it should be mentioned that phraseological units reflect the culture and national mentality of a definite country and nationality; therefore, translation of phraseological units is one of the most important issues of a contemporary translatology. Furthermore, phraseological units are an integral part of any language and knowing these collocations and their adequate interpretation and translation is the proof of proper and adequate translation of the whole expression, fictions and pieces of art. In this context it should be summarized that translators have to follow the norm and usage of the target language when they translate phraseological units.

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³ Ivanova, I. V. (1999). Translation Challenges of Phraseological Units (on the Basis of German Economic Texts). Proceedings ROSI, 3, 47-51